

ISic3361

I.Sicily inscription 3361

Language

Sikel

Type

funerary (?)

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

30.09.13

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Euboia

Place of origin (modern)

Licodia Eubea

Provenance

chance find in 1983 by the group 'A.L.B.A.C.A.' near indigenous
necropolis of contrada Serrapiccola

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 97761

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 644866

Bibliography

Agostiniani, L. 1992. Les parlers indigenes de la Sicile pregreccque. *Lalies*. 11: 126-157.

Cordano, F. 2012. Iscrizioni monumentali dei Siculi. *Aristonothos*. 4: 165-184. At 168 fig.10

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3361. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388446>